

THE ROLE OF THE CULTURE OF COMMUNICATION IN MODERN EDUCATION
AND EDUCATION

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Abstract: In the article, one of the important and urgent issues of this day is the culture of people's behavior. At the same time, its unique aspects in the educational process are highlighted. The importance of the culture of interaction in improving the quality of education has been thoroughly analyzed.

Key words: Politeness, culture, relation, attitude, mode of thinking, rithorics, society, person, the culture of communication, good deeds, the culture of etiquette.

Human is considered the glory and honor of the whole being. In this sense, man stands on a higher status than all the creatures in the universe with his beauty and honor. All the blessings in this bright world are created for man. He was given a mind, a language, thinking, speech, understanding, insight.

A spiritually perfect person has been the eternal dream of our great grandfathers since ancient times and has reached today. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev said, "The tomorrow and well-being of our planet depends on how our children become human beings and mature. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of the idea of violence.

The human race acquires knowledge by means of its mind, understands and controls the world thanks to knowledge. "Abdullah Awlani says with wisdom that the oldest of people is perfect, murshidi, the only one, the one who works the soul, the one who starts the mind. Man is distinguished from animals by his speech and mind. At this moment, under the shadow of human intelligence, he is protected from harm and oppression. It is the mind of the people who captured the animals of the earth, tied them by their necks, and put the ends of the ropes in their hands. [2,63].

His behavior manifests itself depending on the harmony of his inner and outer world. As Fitrat says, "A person should be as he shows himself, or show as he is" [5,2]. In this respect, his culture, behavior, actions in the system of relationships stand out as the basis of his spiritual image. The spiritual image of a person is expressed in his behavior, character traits, his behavior and communication culture.

He can express his inner world, feelings, and hopes only in the process of dealing and communication. According to the rules of etiquette, everyone should respect others if they want to be respected and respected by others. After all, the spoken word or phrase has a positive or negative effect on a person depending on the tone. It is important to know that having some wealth, a high position, even old age or mental disorder does not give the right to be rude to others. As Ibn Sina stated: "In order for a person to always be kind and patient, he should not offend other people, should not spoil his language, and should be good-natured" [3,109].

As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted, "For us, the transaction society is a social space, in this space the law prevails, and it does not prevent a person from self-improvement, on the contrary. helps. The interests of a person help to fully

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realize his rights and freedoms. At the same time, the rights and freedoms of other people cannot be discriminated against. That is, freedom and obedience to the law apply at the same time. complement each other and require each other" [1,554].

In fact, the stability of the society in every way depends on the system of mutual relations of its inhabitants, mutual relations, and the dialectic of behavior and relations. If we paint nature, we can feel the interaction of every creature in it. If the flowers spread their pleasant radiance around and delight the heart, the birds give a special charm to the nature through their chirping and create a way of communication. And in people, this process occurs in relation to the members of the society surrounding them, based on their inner world, mental state, and character traits. Considering communication culture as a work in progress, it is only up to the creators to ensure that to what extent it warms to the heart and gives sincerity. Pleasant communication also goes straight to the human heart. In this respect, a person should strive to have his own creativity, that is, his own culture of behavior, for his behavior at one or another level. Everyone working in the education system should take this issue seriously. Because today's demand for knowledge requires good behavior every day. Any soul that wants knowledge will definitely be attracted to beautiful manners, beautiful speech and expression.

In modern education and training, it is important for every teacher-coach to have a speech culture. The speech of the teacher is important in ensuring the thorough mastering of subjects by students during the educational process. The correct pronunciation of each letter and sound in the teacher's speech has its own significance. A loud student, student feels like he is being cheated during an individual conversation. This can create a feeling of distrust towards the teacher. Some experts say that sound is an innate quality. But current experimental physiology confirms that it is possible to change the quality of sound. Today, several training complexes have been developed for speech technique. They are mainly based on the experience of theater pedagogy and improve the skills of breathing, sound generation and meaningful expression during speaking, which allows the teacher to convey the content of his speech to the students more fully.

In this respect, a person with a high culture of behavior:

- loves and serves his country, people, motherland with loyalty;
- preserves the material and spiritual wealth of the society like the apple of an eye and increases them;
- learns, appreciates and observes the teachings and traditions of our ancestors;
- follows the holy books, laws and decisions with duty and responsibility.
- values himself, his family, relatives, comrades, people.

The culture of interaction is an important link and key of universal culture.

It appears in the following cases:

- ensures the well-being and social awareness of every citizen, the social well-being of the whole society, personal awareness;
- teaches citizens to observe equality before the law, regardless of their race, nationality, social origin, religion, social status;
- culture of dealings - preservation of all the material and spiritual wealth created in the course of the entire historical development of mankind, leads to their increase;

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- it nourishes the culture, spirituality, education, traditions of the citizens of the country formed over the centuries, the immortal heritage of our ancestors;
- serves to preserve the ideas of human duty, responsibility, justice and truth, freedom and independence;
- teaches to actively use the achievements and successes achieved in the course of the democratic development of culture in order for citizens to have a conscious attitude to them.

As long as we live as a member of a certain society, while we work in it, our interaction with each other is the basis for all-round spiritual development of the society in which we live. It is necessary to establish the types and culture of interaction and communication between people who are members of our society today. First of all, the specific behavior of each historical period, as well as the rules and norms of the law, forms a specific culture of communication and communication between teachers and students, parents and children, young men and women, and determines the spiritual image of a person. The main goal is to adapt the behavior and communication between today's youth to the moral requirements of society.

With the emergence of human society, the need for communication between people was felt. Mutually appropriate communication of members of society with each other became the basis for comprehensive development of this society. Communication culture is a concept that does not belong to which nationality a person belongs to, but on the contrary, it refers to a certain country and the geographical area where a person lives. Communication is actually a mirror of the human heart that determines the relationship between people. Behavior is considered a form of morality, and it is possible to see what kind of worldview each person has, and his knowledge from his behavior. In addition, communication is a means of communication between people. The main tool in communication is language, and language can be considered as a "communication tool" in a positive sense. Communication is considered an information process, in which two-way information transmission and reception occurs between the speaker and the listener. The transaction takes place within the framework of mutual relations.

In order to improve visibility in relationships, a person should have a high level of communication culture. A perfect study of the culture of communication will lift the spirits not only of the speaker but also of the listener.

In fact, etiquette is a component of moral culture. "Culture" is derived from the Arabic word and in ancient times it meant Medina, urbanity, education, upbringing. Today, in the encyclopedic dictionary, philosophy is defined as "a unique method of human activity reflected in nature and interactions", and in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, education is defined as "education, intelligence and enlightenment" [4,63].

Therefore, an enlightened and cultured person is understood as a person who can provide material and spiritual nourishment for the society and contribute to their development, physical and spiritual development due to his education and training. Culture is a creative spiritual activity of humanity mobilized to rebuild nature, society and its self, based on the assimilation of experiences expressed in one or another cultural wealth in all spheres of being and consciousness. Recognizing the unity of material and spiritual factors of culture can be understood as looking at it from an individual perspective.

If we look at it from the point of view of the individual, the material needs of citizens are satisfied with the help of spiritual factors, and spiritual factors are formed on the basis of materiality. This is an epistemological view of culture. Academician E. Yusupov gives the

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following description of culture: The culture of interaction accelerates the process of human civilization as a process that improves a person spiritually and materially. A person can learn the culture of treatment not only in the family, in kindergartens, schools and universities, but also throughout life. As a person grows and develops, the culture of communication grows and discovers new aspects.

The process of forming a culture of behavior in students ensures that they are followed, it is effective and effective. Research shows that there are several principles in this regard: First, the principle of idealism and goal orientation. It is known that the strategic goal of our country is to build a strong democratic legal state with an open foreign policy and a transactional society, the development of such a society is inextricably linked with the transactional culture. Society relies on national ideas and ideology. The role of the culture of behavior in creating the principle of idealism is incomparable.

Secondly, on the principle of social orientation, any education comes from the rule of preparing a person for a social and happy life. It is known that the educational institution is considered a social institution and aims to meet the educational and educational needs of the state. This principle also requires the socialization of the process of forming a culture of behavior.

Thirdly, in the principle of striking the old ideological views and distortions in the content of consciousness and behavior, it is envisaged to fundamentally reform the field of education, to completely free it from the distortions left over from the past. In this regard, various activities are carried out, and in the process of preparing students for inter-ethnic communication, they are faced with the tasks of forming citizenship qualities in them, clarifying the fundamental nature of the culture of behavior in their minds. Therefore, the culture of behavior is considered an important link and key of universal culture, and it is a sign of spiritual perfection of a person.

One of the characteristics of transactional culture that is manifested in the signs of perfection is its unity with moral and legal culture. It is known that any state separately controls the activities and discipline of its citizens. The culture of treatment shows a person's spiritual maturity and education. That is why a cultured person is respected among the people. The culture of treatment is a valuable quality that increases human qualities and human value. Education is the true fruit of education. The culture of behavior, which is considered as the support of the mind, is a valuable quality that increases human qualities, the value of a person, it is the honor and wisdom of all qualities.

The culture of treatment is manifested in the homeland, society, nation, history, language, customs, and actions. Looking after the interests of society, being responsible, realizing responsibility, is a characteristic of a person who has a culture of dealing. Because responsibility defines a specific standard of conscious activity, society, family and life. The more a person strives for a life of dealing in his imagination, the more he realizes and understands his own defects. The culture of communication is a reflection of a person's inner world. A person shows his identity through this mirror and sees himself.

oday, there are different views on spiritual perfection and the education of individuals, and its reflection can be observed in the extent to which the culture of behavior has been acquired.

The formation of a culture of behavior in the upbringing of a morally mature person, the social and professional qualities of the teacher's readiness for innovative activities are directly related not only to the economic and financial situation in the educational institution, but also directly to the demand for these qualities and the culture of behavior. Educators who have formed

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a culture of dealing with innovative ideas, the main basis of management of the educational institution is education in the classroom or auditorium, i.e., proper management of the lesson process, making clear decisions.

As the construction of civil society is considered as today's task, its main basis is the members of the society with a culture of dealing. Abu Nasr Farabi states that "spirituality is a sign of development, real development is not in the wealth or the size of the city, the abundance of wealth, the abundance of crops, but the cultural image of a person who has matured in this environment."

To sum up, it is easy for a person who has matured the culture of communication to get his place in society, because in any situation, sweet words light up the sleepy imagination of a person, awaken sincere feelings for him.

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